

The influence of Background Music in Film on Emotional Priming

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Declaration

I declare that this thesis that I have submitted to Dublin Business School for the award of BA (Hons) Psychology is the result of my own investigations, except where otherwise stated, where it is clearly acknowledged by references. Furthermore, this work has not been submitted for any other degree.

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Date: 30/03/2023

Acknowledgements

At the age of 39, after a long career of 10 years in the field of HR in Brazil, deciding to start a second college, in another country, in a different language was not an easy decision. At first, my husband and I came just to learn English and return to our country, but life had other plans for us. So, my thanks and love go out to him, who not only embarked on the same adventure as me but decided to take the same course! Love, thank you so much for holding my hand all this time and not letting me delve into the darkness I've been immersed in these past few months. Now is the time to look ahead, and reap the fruits of our hard work here on the Emerald Isle for the last four years. I would also like to thank my family, even though they are far away, they always supported me and embraced my decisions with affection and love.

Abstract

Music is a constant presence in everyday life and a powerful way in which humans express their feelings. To what extent is music capable of interfering with the way we express our emotions? Is music capable of changing it? This study explored the role of background music in movies in priming our perceived emotions and influencing our interpretation of a scene. Volunteers (N=83) from the general population participate in this online experiment and were randomly allocated to three groups. The first two groups received the scene with manipulated background positive and negative music while the third group (control) received the original scene without background music. Results found a significant priming effect on both congruent and incongruent audio-visual stimuli, in accordance with previous studies. Future research should deepen the analysis using different sources of investigation to broaden the insights into music and its relationship with emotions that generates real-life action in different domains.

1. Introduction

1.1 Music Relevance to Emotion

Music is everywhere. Music is a powerful way of affecting society morally (Noviana & Simanjuntak, 2022), emotionally (Panwar et al., 2019) and culturally (Khasanova, 2020). Its influence on human behaviour has been emphasised through research as an important factor in communication, development and social connection (Loersch & Arbuckle, 2013). Music is also proven to be strongly relevant to our personal values (Gardikiotis & Baltzis, 2012), the development of thinking, creativity, problem-solving and reasoning processes (cognitive performance) and mental flexibility (MacDonald et al., 2013). Music has also an influence on decreasing conflict and promoting interindividual understanding (Alcorta et al., 2008). Music-relevant relation with cinema is linked to its ability to set the tone, evoke feelings and develop a unique bond connection between the audience and the movie characters. With its ability to enhance the impact of visual storytelling and deepen the emotional resonance of movies, music has long been a potent instrument in the world of cinema.

Music has the power to immerse us in a film's universe, up the tension in a scene, and elicit a wide range of feelings in us, whether through a sweeping symphonic score or a thoughtfully chosen soundtrack. The appropriate music can inspire terror, arouse nostalgia, improve romantic situations, and foster suspense. However, the emotional aspects that the audience of a movie has during the film presentation are not always consistent with the director's intention. A study by Tian et al (2017) showed that to increase the possibility to achieve emotional induction in an audience the use of temporal context, dialogues, and aesthetical content (music included) are important aspects to be considered. Another important element to consider is the metaphor aspect that music and sound have in filmmaking. To enhance the emotional and physical effects of a fictional character or object in a film, sound

designers often use conceptual and metaphorical merging of emotional and physical characteristics between sound and pictures. By using words metaphorically, such as "force" or "balance," sound designers can guide the viewer's perception of the film unconsciously, creating an audio-visual and emotional gestalt of the objects (Fahlenbrach, K., 2008).

The drama, action, and romance on screen can be brought to life through the use of music in a way that can have an impact on us long after the movie has ended. Music has so become a crucial component. Bernard Herrmann, an American widely recognized composer (1911-1975) whose relevant soundtracks permeated such classics as 'Vertigo' (1958), 'Psycho' (1960) and 'Taxi Driver' (1976) among others, also emphasized the importance of music as a communicator of inner thoughts of the characters as well as a mood-inducer, directing audience's emotions, resulting in a seamless audio-visual experience. The aim of this study is to analyse the capacity that background music in film has on communicating and inducing emotional states and how the manipulation of music might be able to convey dynamic and complex, emotional messages.

1.2 How the Brain process information and Influences Emotion

A large part of the frontal region of the brain is involved in processing the elements that compose music. The rhythmic process takes place in the motor and premotor cortex (Popescu et.al, 2004), the time and musical mode process take place in the middle frontal gyrus (Khalifa et.al., 2005) and the emotional aspect of music is generally associated with the medial prefrontal cortex (Phan et.al., 2002). Although there is still an on whether music really evokes emotions (Juslin, 2019), studies have shown changes in the sympathetic nervous system associated with physiological arousal evoked in the subcortical regions of the brain (e.g. Amygdala) that activate the hypothalamic and the autonomic nervous system to release arousal hormones. The emotional stimuli (valence) in the left amygdala are associated with pleasant

music while an increase in unpleasant responses was observed in the right amygdala (Brattico,2015).

As the use of neuroimaging advances, researchers are applying multivariate tools of factor analysis and multidimensional scaling and being able to classify both functional and affective dimensions as well as discrete emotional patterns of human brain activity (Kragel & LaBar, 2016). The use of imaging is linked to the growing need for scientists to develop emotional representations and be able to understand how emotions are decoded in the brain. As proposed by the *Congruent-Associationist Model* (Cohen et.al.,2006) the mental framework of information processing includes both bottom-up (audiovisual stimuli producing a reaction) and top-down (stimuli activating past experiences) processes that converge an emotional experience to the working memory. According to his model, the degree of congruence between the listener's own emotional associations and the emotion they perceive in the music is what determines how emotionally charged they feel when they hear a piece of music. That is, the emotional reaction to music depends not only on its acoustic qualities but also on the listener's unique experiences, personal associations and how congruent the perceived emotion of the music and the individual's personal combinations are. Despite the visual effect being the first component that filmmakers focus on, cognitive researchers seek to investigate the effect that the auditory process has upon the visual process and how can music anticipate in the audience's mind what comes next in a scene or how the character will react (Petersen et al., 2017). As could be seen, visual perception is not a passive process. The cognitive structures are activated in our brain to interpret the world and it will be influenced by the emotional state of the observer (McDonald et al.,2022).

1.3 Priming Effect and Background Music

Priming is a concept in psychology used to explain the phenomenon in which people are exposed to a stimulus that might influence their emotional response without their awareness by generating a particular mood that carries over into the viewing experience, as a result of the activation of mental representations (schemas) that interfere/facilitate subsequent behaviour (Molden, 2014). Music's emotion-congruent effect on cognition and memory has been strongly observed in movie scenes and often elicits intense emotional reactions and demands appropriate interpretation and meaning processing (Timmers et.al., 2012). It has been demonstrated that mood- music affects how viewers interpret visual information and narrative (Boltz, 2001), as well as how well they remember specific movie sequences (Boltz, 2004), all of which can be related to the music's ability to draw viewers' attention to particular details within film samples. Emotional, visual and auditory information when emotionally congruent reinforces each other (Baumgartner et.al., 2006). The same was observed in ambiguous emotional stimuli, where even when asked to ignore the presence of music, it still influenced emotional evaluation (Spreckelmeyer et.al., 2006). The ability background music has on inducing people's moods may modulate people's internal representations and change the way they perceive the world (Jolij & Meurs, 2011). In the cinematic context, music helps to give meaning to a scene, enhancing the film's interpretation and maximising the narrative ambiguity (Cohen, 2000). One of the most important functions of the soundtrack is to make sense of the characters' thoughts, moods and feelings. Since music not only arouses emotion but also portrays it, musical moods are made to both set the atmosphere of a scene and make the audience experience themselves and feel those feelings, as a result of a 'cognitivist' (intellectual empathy) and 'emotivist' (emotional empathy) combination (Kivy,1989).

1.4 Music induction and Emotional models

Scholars have long theorised that music speaks the language of emotions (Meyer, 1956; Brown, 2000). According to this perspective, people frequently listen to the music due to its potent emotional influence. There is a strong correlation between certain musical elements and various emotions, including happiness and melancholy. Empirical studies on the emotional interpretation of music suggest that elements such as tempo, dissonance, pitch height and loudness of music are greatly associated with emotional expression (Thompson & Quinto, 2011). All these elements combined create a kind of 'code' that composers and musicians use to communicate emotion through music. Any change in the way these codes are passed on can cause changes in the emotional interpretation and effective experience that each encounter (Justin & Laukka, 2003; Ilie & Thompson, 2006; Ilie & Thompson, 2011). Listeners frequently link positive emotions to quicker tempos and major modes, whereas negative emotions to slower tempos and minor modes (Hunter et.al., 2008; Dalla Bella et.al.,2001; Gagnon & Peretz, 2003). Russell's two-dimensional model called *Circumplex* (1980) mapped emotions on arousal (activity) and valence (positive/negative) levels. Based on his model, arousal and valence emotions can be interconnected (feeling happy and calm as well as feeling sad and energetic), which explains why emotional responses can evoke mixed feelings and perceptions and can be produced by changes in tempo and mode effects (Hunter et.al., 2010). Another model, the *Discrete emotion model* argues that each emotion has a specific representation and classification by its functions and universal character in primary emotions with different developmental functions (Rosenberg & Ekman, 1994). According to this concept, emotions like joy, sadness, anger, fear, disgust, and surprise can be easily distinguished from one another. Furthermore, it suggests that by generating sound patterns that are connected to specific emotional states, music might elicit feelings in listeners.

For instance, sluggish, minor-key melodies and sombre lyrics may be indicative of melancholy music, while brisk, uplifting rhythms and cheery lyrics may indicate joyous music.

Aguilar et.al., (2019) meta-analysis of studies that merged discrete emotions and circumplex models suggested that movies are effective mood inducers and that negative induction has a substantial impact size for both degrees of arousal and valence, supporting earlier research that suggested negative mood induction to be more potent than positive emotional induction (Westermann et.al., 1996; Gerrard-Hesse et.al., 1994). From a cognitive perspective, the *Cognitive Load Theory* suggests that the amount of cognitive processing required to understand and enjoy music influences an individual's emotional response. As our brain has to process multiple elements of music simultaneously such as rhythm, harmony, melody and lyrics, the greater the complexity of the music, the greater the cognitive load required to process these elements and understand the musical emotional message (Atkinson & Shiffrin, 1968). Additionally, personal music preferences, past experiences and background culture also influence how people related to music. That model explains why the emotional response to music is different among individuals, even if they experience listening to the same piece of music, chances are they express their feelings differently.

1.5 Previous research

Most of the experiments focus on non-diegetic (underscore) music as a background. This music cannot be heard by the characters in the movie but it has a paramount role in the audience's understanding of the narrative (Cieslak, 2019). The use of this specific technique is to establish an ideal atmosphere, enhance feelings and manipulate the audience's perceived emotions. The background music also works to emphasize themes, and characters' personality traits and give the scenes a sense of continuity.

A study using short films excerpt with a moral dilemma theme with different background soundtracks conducted by Cunnington (2020) found that the emotion induced by the music produced some influence on people's moral judgment regarding the character's action. The research was mainly based on previous work from Steffens (2020) which assumed that the emotion-inducing music which is either positive or negative would either enhance or reduce positive/negative emotions compared with a neutral group (without music). This was measured by asking the respondents questions based on a survey. Steffens found mixed results, while the positive music condition was found to have a significant effect on emotion and directly influenced the participant's moral judgement. The same was not found in the other three conditions, which were observed to be associated with the participant's individual moral foundation. The moral foundation was measured by the use of the German moral foundation MFQ-30 (Bowman, 2010; Graham et al., 2011).

Other research using congruent background music (Congruent background music refers to music that is aligned with the tone, mood, or theme of a particular situation, event, or activity) showed people's amplified empathy for the main character compared to the original version of the clip without music. Soundtrack and visual stimuli congruent were also argued to be more effective in appraising emotions than an incongruent soundtrack in Bottin & Arcuri's study (2002). The main change in empathy rate was observed in a 'self' level that reperussed a change towards how they saw the character (Brown et.al.,2019). Earlier research conducted by Boltz (2001) using ambiguous film clips that could be interpreted freely by the participant also supported the role of music as a direct influence on cognitive processes (mood-consistent information) over the inconsistent affective valence. Ambiguous character reaction (a situation where a character's emotional or psychological response to a particular event or stimulus is unclear or uncertain) followed by melodrama and thriller music also demonstrates to what extent musical schemas can influence how much an audience will like or dislike a character as

well as the respondents were able to recognize objects with thin the film (Hoeckner et.al., 2011). The same differences in perception on incongruent trials were observed in a study conducted by Tan et.al. (2008) where dissonance combinations lead to a different emotional perception of the characters.

In summary previous research on the topic has used mostly moral dilemmas scenes to study the impact of music on the audience. Although the present study has as a main goal to analyse the priming effect of background music on the participant's interpretation of their emotions in the same manner as some of the previous studies, slightly different approaches were adopted such as the use of the *Discrete Emotion Questionnaire (DEQ)* and no moral dilemmas scenes on conducting the experiment.

1.6 Rationale & Hypothesis

A two-dialogue excerpt from the movie *'No Country for Old Men'* has been chosen. It involves the interaction of the main character (Anton Chigurh) with two other characters. In the two chosen scenes of the actual movie, the narrative makes it clear that the main character has peculiar personality traits but there is no direct information that he works as a hitman. Later, the respondents were required to point out what perceived emotions they felt toward the scenes through a Likert-scale questionnaire. From this point, we investigate the influence of positive and negative musical schemas upon the actual behaviour of the character. We select music that has a positive feeling and music that has a negative feeling for each of the emotions. Negative feeling music should intensify emotions and anger while positive feeling music should intensify a cheerful feeling. The focus is on the music's ability to prime emotion which can influence participants and lead to biased perceived emotion reports.

The same movie excerpt will be used in all three conditions. The first group received the scenes with positive background music, the second group with positive background music

and the control group received the scenes in the original version (without sound). The first hypothesis assumes that the three groups will show a significant difference in perceived emotion among different experimental media conditions (H1). The group that watched the movie clip with negative background music was assumed to rate higher levels of unpleasant emotions than the participants from the control group (H2). The group that watched the video with positive music as a condition, we presumed to have higher rates of pleasant emotions than the control group (H3). Positive music group, we assume to score high on positive emotion compared to the negative music group (H4). Finally, the negative music group was expected to score high on unpleasant emotions compared to the positive music group (H5).

The relevance of this research lies in the fact that music is a significant part of an individual's life and the way people express themselves, as well as being an active part of the culture and interaction that unites individuals socially. In the same way, cinema is inserted into our daily life not only as a form of leisure but also as a means of integrating us into other cultures. The combination of these two arts has proven to exert a great influence on how people interact in society. As pointed out by Storm (2016), "characters are invented by writers not just to tell a story, they become a vehicle for our own experience, representing and standing for us, being our experimental surrogates." Understanding the extent to which music interferes and primes our emotions, affecting the way we judge a character is a relevant starting point for observing the external impact on emotions. A better understanding of this topic can help researchers in the emotional field, working on models and approaches that help the use of music to enhance positive attitudes as well as improve mood and the quality of human interactions in a real-life setting.

2. Method

2.1 Participants

Participants in this experiment were randomly sampled from the general population with no exclusion criteria. As the emotional response was the nature of this research, no demographic requirements such as gender, age or income were asked. A total of 83 participants were randomly allocated to 3 different conditions, 25 participants were allocated to the control group which received the original scene with no background music, 23 to the group with positive background music included and 35 to the group with negative background music. Facebook and LinkedIn Social platforms were used to spread the experiment and gather participants as well as the Survey Swap's website (<https://surveyswap.io>), which is intended for researchers from various countries, especially students, that make available their surveys and respond to others' surveys in exchange. The consent given by the participants was done through the online form available before the beginning of the experiment together with the Ethical guidelines. Any rewards were provided and the participation was given voluntarily by the participants.

2.2 Design

This true-experimental between-subject study took the form of an online experiment and aimed to analyse the impact of background music (non-diegetic) commonly used in films on people's perceived emotions and to what extent they can prime the audience's perception of the scene. The participants were randomly assigned to three groups and requested to watch two video excerpts from the movie '*No Country for Old Men*' and answer the *Discrete Emotion Questionnaire – DEQ* designed to measure self-reported emotions. The duration of the experiment was estimated to last 10 to 15 minutes. The control group watched excerpts from the original film (without music), the first watched the scenes with positive music in the background and the second group with negative music in the background. The participants

were not referred to the musical element present in the scenes so that it would not influence the perception required in the experiment. Positive and negative music inserted on the scene was the independent variable (IV) used to interfere with the dependent variable (DV) emotional perception reported by the participants. Hypotheses were suggested as follows:

H1: There will be a significant difference in perceived emotion scores in the three groups.

H2: Negative background music group will score higher on negative emotion compared to the control group.

H3: Positive music group will score higher on positive emotion compared to the control group.

H4: Positive music group will score higher on positive emotion compared to the negative music group.

H5: Negative music group will score higher on negative emotion compared to the positive music group.

2.3 Materials / Apparatus

2.3.1 Materials and Apparatus

The *Microsoft Form* was the platform where the experiment was developed and distributed to the participants. To enter the experiment, the participant was required to have a computer or cell phone with internet access. The use of headphones was suggested to improve the quality of the sound and the individual experience. No specific equipment, technology or brand was required. The information sheet and consent form were presented before the beginning of the experiment (Appendix A) as well as a short instruction section (Appendix B). *VSDC Video Edit Software* was used to edit the videos and include the music stimuli (Appendix C). Lastly, the debrief section was displayed at the end of the study (Appendix D).

2.3.2 Film Excerpt Selections

The two audio-visual stimuli applied in the experiment were extracted from the American movie *No Country for Old Men* (Coen, J. & Coen, E.; 2007). The criteria adopted for the chosen scenes diverged from previous studies that used non-verbal excerpts (Hoeckner et al., 2011) or scenes whose characters were immersed in a moral dilemma or distressing situation (Steffens, 2020; Brown et al., 2020; Cunnington, 2020). The two montages are followed by the lead character Anton Chigurh and his peculiar personality traits interacting with two other characters, however, without previous knowledge of his profession as a hitman, the participant in the experiment has no awareness of his dark nature. The reason behind this video choice is to understand if the background music has a prime effect on influencing the perceived emotion of the participant without their full awareness of it.

2.3.3 Music's Stimuli Selection

The original scenes used in the experiment do not have background music and, therefore, were set up for the control group. Conversely, the two experimental groups accessed the scenes with two different background musical stimuli. The instrumental songs used in the manipulation of the scenes were taken from the *Epidemic Sound* royalty-free website (<https://www.epidemicsound.com/music/featured/>). To stimulate feelings and enhance positive emotions in the participant, songs taken from the country music album *Just as Good* (by Eric Feinberg) and *Gravel in my Shoe* (by Harry Edvino) were used. Conversely, to evoke negative feelings towards the scene, the songs *Once you've had a taste* (by Christian Andersen) and *Trapped in the Sewers* (by Experia) were taken from the album *Horror & creepy music*.

2.3.4 Discrete Emotion Questionnaire (DEQ)

The questionnaire (Appendix E) used to access the emotions perceived by the participants was the *Discrete Emotion Questionnaire* (DEQ). This tool was designed to address the emotional aspect on a discrete level, rather than a dimensional approach and is sensitive to eight distinctive emotional main states namely: disgust, anger, anxiety, fear, happiness, sadness, desire and relaxation (Bastian et.al., 2016). Each of these emotions presents 4 subscales as emotions derived from the main one (discrete). In total, 32 discrete emotional statements were displayed and the participant rated each one on a 7- point Likert Scale varying from 1(Not at all) to 7 (An extreme amount). The display of discrete emotions is distributed as follows: *Anger* (anger, rage, mad and pissed off), *Disgust* (grossed out, nausea, sickened and revulsion), *Fear* (terror, scared, panic, fear), *Anxiety* (dread, anxiety, nervous, worry), *Sadness* (sad, grief, lonely, empty), *Relaxation* (easy going, chilled out, calm, relaxation), *Happiness* (happy, satisfaction, enjoyment, liking) and *Desire* (wanting, desire, craving, longing). The final score will be the sum of the items for each discrete emotion category. The distinction of this instrument lies in the fact that it allows to access a broad array of emotions that, in some circumstances, can be mixed with other emotions and for this reason, it is not perceived when analysed from a unique emotional perspective. The reliability for all subscales measurements is high - Cronbach's α s > 0.80 [Table 1].

Table 1: Cronbach α

Subscale	Study 2	Study 3	Study 4
Anger subscale (anger, mad, pissed off, rage)	0.97	0.96	0.94
Disgust subscale (grossed out, revulsion, sickened, nausea)	0.88	0.89	0.92
Fear subscale (terror, scared, fear, panic)	0.92	0.94	0.93
Anxiety subscale (worry, anxiety, dread, nervous)	0.90	0.93	0.93
Sadness subscale (lonely, grief, sad, empty)	0.85	0.89	0.82
Desire subscale (wanting, craving, longing, desire)	*	0.86	0.93
Relaxation subscale (calm, relaxation, chilled out, easygoing)	*	0.91	0.93
Happiness subscale (happy, enjoyment, satisfaction, liking)	*	0.97	0.96

Note: Numbers represent Cronbach's α ;

* indicates that the subscale was not included in this study.

2.4 Procedure

The experiment was carried out in an online environment. In *Section 1* participants had access to the information sheet. The objective of the study about the investigation of emotion related to movie scenes was specified followed by the confidentiality of the data collected, risks that might impose and the right to withdraw at any time. After reading and giving their consent, the *Section 2* participants were redirected to the instruction which consisted in a brief preview explanation and orientation that proceed to the movie's excerpts presentation. It also informed the total duration of the two scenes (around 5'33'') and the overall time to complete being from 10 to 15 minutes. *Section 3* consisted of the presentation of the movie excerpts itself. *Section 4* redirects participants to fill up the *Discrete Emotion Questionnaire* Likert scale of self-reported emotion. Finally, in *Section 5* a debrief was offered. Participants were thanked for completing the experiment and provided with supportive contacts in case of any distress experienced they need to address regards the experience.

2.5 Ethics

The design of the experiment was carried out regarding the ethical guidelines of The Psychological Society of Ireland (PSI) as well as the DBS Ethical Guidelines. The choice of video stimuli was carefully made to not bring up any sensitive or highly distressing topics to the experiment that could make it unavailable to the public in general. After approval by the ethics committee that evaluated my research proposal, I made it viable on my Social Media platforms and the SurveySwap website. The introduction part of the experiment included relevant ethical considerations for the participant's awareness as follows:

Objective and risk involved: it was clarified to the participants that the content of the experiment was related to film and its ability to enable emotions in the audience. It was also informed that the content of the video used did not provide sensitive content, however, the

researcher's contact was made available in case the participant required any further explanation or assistance.

Confidentiality: no demographic (age, gender, income) or personal (name, email address) information was requested in this experiment. Even so, participants were informed that all information collected is confidential and anonymous and has the sole purpose of academic use. It was also stressed that all information will be eliminated after five years.

Right to withdraw: for whatever reason and at any time participants were informed they can leave the experiment without explanation and also, they can request that their answer be removed from the record.

Debrief session: if any questions or issues arise as a result of participating in the experiment, participants were encouraged to contact the researcher by email that was made available, as well as the contact of support groups.

3. Results

3.1 Descriptive Statistics

The study counted 83 participants over 18 years old. Participants were randomly assigned to 3 groups (positive, negative and no music). [Table 2] shows the descriptive statistics of the 8 compound variables of emotional valence.

	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis
Total Anger	10.87	5.40	.467	-.707
Total Disgust	9.60	4.97	.550	-.970
Total Fear	10.25	5.20	.620	-.416
Total Anxiety	11.88	5.13	.463	.313
Total Sadness	7.99	4.69	1.465	2.656
Total Desire	6.78	4.22	1.557	1.407
Total Relaxation	9.06	4.63	1.193	2.038
Total Happiness	8.05	4.96	1.017	-.052

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Based on the table presented it can be seen that most of the variables have positive skewness. Variables that demonstrated higher deviations (Happiness and Desire) were analysed by a non-parametric statistical test. Histograms of those two variables are listed below (Figures 1 & 2):

Figure 1: histogram of total happiness variable with a skewed curve.

Figure 2: histogram of total desire variable with a skewed curve.

3.2 Inferential Statistics

3.2.1 Reliability

Firstly, the reliability and internal consistency of the eight subscales have been assessed through Cronbach's alpha. All the subscales proved to be very consistent [Table 3].

Table 3. Cronbach's alpha α

Anger	0.846
Disgust	0.848
Fear	0.886
Anxiety	0.832
Sadness	0.847
Desire	0.874
Relaxation	0.715
Happiness	0.896

3.2.2 The Effect of Background Music

In this study, the inferential statistics will be divided by hypothesis and then the eight emotional valences will be analysed separately to facilitate and have a proximal interpretation of where the differences between the groups rely on.

It was first hypothesized that there will be a difference in perceived emotion scores among the three groups. The one-way ANOVA analyses test was performed. One for total positive emotions (desire, relaxation, and happiness) and the second for total negative emotions (anger, disgust, fear, and sadness).

A one-way analysis of variance suggested (*Figure 3*) that the compound of total positive emotions differed significantly between the three groups ($F(2, 80) = 3.98, p < .001, \eta^2 = .818$) with a large effect size. More specifically, Tukey HSD post hoc analyses highlighted that the positive music group differ significantly from the negative music group (Mean difference = 8.77, $p = .018$, CI [95%] 1.16, 16.38). No significant difference was found between the control group (no music) and the positive music group, nor between the negative music group. Therefore, the null is rejected.

Figure 3: Estimated Marginal Means of total positive emotions

Following, A one-way analysis of variance (*Figure 4*) showed that the compound of total negative emotions differed significantly between the three groups ($F(2, 80) = 10.54, p < .001, \eta^2 = .209$) with a large effect size. More specifically Tukey HSD post hoc analyses

highlighted that the positive music group differ significantly from the negative music group (Mean difference = -19.84, $p < .001$, CI [95%] -30.86, -8.82) and from the control (no music) group (Mean difference = -17.19, $p = .002$, CI [95%] -29.05, -5.33). No significant difference was found between the no music group and the negative music group. Therefore, the null is rejected.

Figure 4: Estimated Marginal Means of total negative emotions.

For our second hypothesis, it was assumed that the negative group will have higher scores on negative emotions than the control group, so an independent sample t-test was applied.

An independent samples t-test found that there wasn't a statistically significant difference between negative emotions in the negative music group ($M = 56.89$, $SD = 15.32$) and control group ($M = 54.24$, $SD = 14.45$) ($t(58) = .675$, $p = .502$, CI (95%) -5.20, 10.49). Therefore, the null cannot be rejected.

Thirdly, it was hypothesized that the positive group will have higher scores on positive emotions than the control group, thus an independent sample t-test was performed.

An independent samples t-test found that there wasn't a statistically significant difference between positive emotions in the positive music group ($M = 29.09$, $SD = 10.40$) and the control group ($M = 24.12$, $SD = 13.15$) ($t(46) = 1.44$, $p = .156$, $CI(95\%) -1.96, 11.90$). Therefore, the null cannot be rejected.

For our fourth hypothesis, it was assumed the positive group will have higher scores on positive emotions than the negative music group. An independent sample t-test was used.

An independent samples t-test found that there was a statistically significant difference between positive emotions in the positive music group ($M = 29.09$, $SD = 10.40$) and the negative music group ($M = 20.31$, $SD = 11.13$) ($t(56) = 3.01$, $p = .004$, $CI(95\%) 2.93, 14.61$). Therefore, the null can be rejected.

Lastly, for our fifth hypothesis, we predicted that the negative group will have higher scores on negative emotions than the positive music group using an independent sample t-test.

An independent samples t-test found that there was a statistically significant difference between negative emotions in the positive music group ($M = 37.04$, $SD = 20.82$) and the negative music group ($M = 56.89$, $SD = 15.32$) ($t(56) = -4.179$, $p > .001$, $CI(95\%) -29.35, 10.33$). Therefore, the null can be rejected.

3.2.3 Emotional Valences

The eight emotional valences were analysed separately. For Desire and Happiness, a non-parametric test Kruskal-Wallis was chosen based on the histogram results. Anger, Disgust, Fear, Anxiety, Sadness, and Relaxation were analysed using a One-way ANOVA.

Desire

A Kruskal-Wallis H test showed that the variable desire did not differ significantly between the groups ($\chi^2(2) = 3.82$, $p = .148$). Therefore, the null is not rejected.

Happiness

A Kruskal-Wallis H test showed that the variable happiness differs significantly between the groups ($\chi^2(2) = 19.73, p < .001$). Therefore, the null was rejected.

Anger

A one-way analysis of variance showed that the variable anger did not differ significantly between the three groups ($F(2, 80) = 1.87, p = .161, \eta^2 = .045$). Therefore, the null cannot be rejected.

Anxiety

A one-way analysis of variance showed that variable anxiety differed significantly between the three groups ($F(2, 80) = 9.93, p < .001, \eta^2 = .199$) with a large effect size. More specifically Tukey HSD post hoc analyses highlighted that the positive music group differ significantly from the negative music group (Mean difference = 5.24, $p < .001$, CI [95%] 8.22, 2.26) and the no music group (Mean difference = 4.82, $p = .002$, CI [95%] 8.03, 1.61). no significant difference in anxiety was found between the negative music group and the control music group. Therefore, the null is rejected.

Figure 5: Estimated Marginal Means of total anxiety.

Disgust

A one-way analysis of variance showed that variable disgust differed significantly between the three groups ($F(2, 80) = 7.01, p = .002, \eta^2 = .149$) with a large effect size. More specifically Tukey HSD post hoc analyses highlighted that the positive music group differ significantly from the negative music group (Mean difference = - 4.22, $p = .003$, CI [95%] -7.20, -1.25) and the no music group (Mean difference = -4.32, $p = .005$, CI [95%] -7.52, -1.12). No significant difference in disgust was found between the negative music group and the control group. Therefore, the null is rejected.

Figure 6: Estimated Marginal Means of total disgust.

Fear

A one-way analysis of variance showed that variable fear differed significantly between the three groups ($F(2, 80) = 11.03, p < .001, \eta^2 = .216$) with a large effect size. More specifically Tukey HSD post hoc analyses highlighted that the positive music group differ significantly from the negative music group (Mean difference = - 5.82, $p < .001$, CI [95%] -

8.88, -2.76) and the no music group (Mean difference = -4.23, $p = .007$, CI [95%] -7.53, -.945). no significant difference in fear was found between the negative music group and the control group. Therefore, the null is rejected.

Figure 7: Estimated Marginal Means of total fear.

Sadness

A one-way analysis of variance showed that variable sadness did not differ significantly between the three groups ($F(2, 80) = 1.41$, $p = .249$, $\eta^2 = .034$) Therefore, the null is not rejected.

Relaxation

A one-way analysis of variance showed that variable relaxation did not differ significantly between the three groups ($F(2, 80) = 2.90$, $p = .06$, $\eta^2 = .068$) Therefore, the null is not rejected.

4. Discussion

4.1. Relevant aspects of the study

The main focus of conducting this experiment was to analyse the effect of background music in movies on priming people's perceived emotions in the presence of the same scenes but with different music as stimuli. As a result, the relevance of this study is to understand how music can significantly affect and improve human emotional expression at an individual and social level. This section has lighted on the details explanations of different elements of the results as well as the finding of the analysis to ascertain the study on the influence of background music in film on emotional priming.

After running the statistical ANOVA test, the results of the first hypothesis highlighted the presence of a significantly different score on the emotional perception among the three groups, especially between the ones that have the background music manipulated. In this case, the overall score on positive music was higher compared to the negative music background. These findings are partially in accordance with the Congruent-Associationist mental framework model which stated that people tend to associate new information with congruent previous knowledge to create a new concept (Cohen et.al.,2006). The reason why this model only partially explains this result is the fact that the scene presented to the participants does not have a positive or funny meaning, on the contrary, the dialogue between the characters involves a certain tension. In that case, the Cognitive load theory is the best approach to understanding the divergent finding. In that case, because the schematic structures interpret stimuli differently, the 'cognitive load' can also enhance or hinder emotion perception (Atkinson & Shiffrin, 1968). According to this model, visual and auditory processes do not compete and express separately in the working memory, which corroborates the fact that even presented with a tense dialogue, because of the positive, vibrant music in the background, participants presented higher scores

on positive perceived emotion. It is also in agreement with Steffens's findings (2020) where positive music conditions had a significant priming effect on emotion in the judgement of the scene.

The second and third hypotheses analysed the scores of the positive and negative experimental groups compared to the control group to assess differences in perceived emotion. Again, the no significant results showed that these variables (music and visual content) were explicitly and mutually exclusive and independent, implying that the occurrence of one event did not affect the happenings of the other. This confirmed the variation that existed between these groups and the variables used to determine the priming effect of music. These findings contradict previous research that suggested that congruent background music amplified empathy for the main character (Brown et al., 2019) as well as they are more effective in appraising emotions rather than inconsistent affective valence (Boltz, 2001). As seen in the results, the group manipulated with negative music compared to the control group showed a very low difference in negative emotion ($M=2.65$). In this case, the presence of the background music did not affect or enhance people's perceived emotions compared with the absence of music. Similarly, the group with positive music scored low differences from the control group ($M=4.97$) on positive emotions suggesting that music is not the only factor behind people's perceived emotional response.

Interestingly, significant results were found, this time, by analysing the emotional scores between the two experimental groups. Firstly, the Positive music group and negative music group scores on positive emotions had a mean difference ($M=8.78$), with positive emotions being more appealing in the Positive group ($M=29.09$) than the negative group ($M=20.31$). In addition, negative and positive experimental groups had a significantly high mean score on negative perceived emotion ($M=19.85$), being the negative group responsible for holding the highest score ($M=56.89$). Contradicting the previous hypothesis, these results

suggest that, although the participants of both groups received the same excerpts of scenes from the film, the manipulation of the background music makes them perceive emotion differently. In this case, both positive music enhanced positive perceived feelings and negative music intensified perceived negative feelings. Another point to be observed is that this significant result occurred both in a congruent exposure (tense scene, negative music) and in an incongruent one (tense scene, positive music), suggesting that the emotional reaction to music can occur in both conditions. A similar study conducted by Tan et.al., 2017 observed the same response in participants whose dissonant combination of visual and musical aspects resulted in different emotional perceptions of the characters.

Overall, the analysis of the variables separately suggested that on the positive variables, happiness was the only perceived significantly among the others (relaxation and desire). Conversely, the negative emotion variables had anxiety, disgust and fear perceived significantly among the negative group. The Fear subscales reached significantly higher scores in the negative and control condition as opposed to the positive ones. Similarly, Sadness was experienced more in the negative and no music groups as opposed to the positive music group. As audio-visual integration is a combination of facial expressions and another sort of body language along with music exposure, it makes unclear the specific role of music on emotional perception. However, these findings are consistent with previous studies that suggested congruent visual and auditory stimuli enhance auditory regions (Jeong et.al.,2011) which might explain the negative music significance in the present study. Nevertheless, the same study argued that incongruent visual-auditory stimuli impact visual effect, which was not been observable in this experiment, where the happiness component of positive music acted priming upon perceived emotion diminishing negative elements of the scene and increasing more positive emotional expression.

4.2 Strengths and Limitations

Some of the aspects used in the methodology of this online experiment added novelty characteristics to previous studies. The measurement of the participant's emotional perception using the DEQ questionnaire helped to access positive and negative perceived emotions not only in a broad way as commonly used but in a way that measures multiple emotional states by approaching different manipulations of emotion hence, being more accurate on capturing emotional responses to events. Using the same scenes in all conditions and choosing mixing congruent and incongruent models of visual-auditory stimuli were also essential to eliminate biased reports and enhance their effectiveness in evaluating emotional responses.

Despite the significant results of this study, it also has considerable limitations. Its online context did not allow the researcher to control the interferences and the environment in which the participant chose to perform the task which might have interference with the outcome. As well as it was not taken into account the previous emotional state of the participants which also may have had an impact on the participants' self-reported perceived emotion. Regarding the sample size analysed, it was a compound of 83 participants, a small sample that may decrease the statistical power of the results. Short-time data collection also contributed to the limited number of participants. Concerning the movie excerpts, the choice of scenes from a classic Hollywood film may have biased some responses from participants who had already watched the film before.

4.3 Conclusion and Future Research

To conclude, the influence of background music in film on emotional priming was partially observed and significant, notably affecting the groups in which the positive and negative music were inserted as a priming tool. While negative music performed the enhancing of the tense mood of the scene in a congruent way, positive music worked as a diminisher of

the tension of the scene and provide the participants with positive feelings in an incongruent manner. Findings for all hypotheses partially confirmed that negative and positive music can elicit an emotional reaction from the audience. Similarly, the study also suggested that anger, anxiety, fear, disgust, sadness, desire, happiness, and relaxation had the same probability of occurrence among all three groups regardless of their small effect in some cases.

Based on the results drawn from this study, there are potential directions for future research. Experiments investigating the emotional response to music should include a broader range of different sources of investigation. Physical measurements (e.g., heart rate modulations, skin conductance responses), contrasted types of music (instrumental and vocal music), and different movies genres (romance, comedy, horror, etc) can help the study to gain a more complex understanding of how the emotional process takes place and manifest itself. A following qualitative questionnaire investigating participants' answers also complements and enriches the in-depth analyses. There are several reasons why music evokes emotions. Movies are a classic example of how viewers can "feel" the joys and challenges of characters in a unique way and sometimes with prolonged effect. For this reason, studying the power of music in influencing human life has diverse implications in a variety of domains. It improves scientific understanding of how individuals experience emotion and respond to various stimuli, helps composers and musicians while creating the most effective and moving compositions that resonate with their audience, implicates and marketing and advertising campaign that creates an emotional connection with the target audience and also has a therapeutic application helping individuals to cope with psychological issues. Overall, it can provide insights that generate real-life actions that will benefit people's relationship with their own emotions.

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6. Appendix

A) Information Sheet and Consent Form

**Sample Information sheet and Consent form for Experiment
Information Sheet for study on Film & Emotions**

My name is Karina Moreira Ferreira and I am conducting research in the Department of Psychology that explores how fictional characters in movies are capable of enabling emotions on the audience. This research is being conducted as part of my studies and will be submitted for examination.

You are invited to participate in a research study that will form the basis for an undergraduate thesis. Please read the following information before deciding whether to participate.

What are the objectives of the study? The nature of this study is to understand to what extent characters emotions in a movie can drive our own emotions. A full debrief will be offered after participation, where any questions additional will be answered following participation.

Why have I been asked to participate? I would like to collect information from different people regarding their emotions towards a fictional character.

- Participant must have internet access
- The use of headphones is indicated for better appreciation of the video but is not mandatory.
- Must over 18 years of age
-

What does participation involve? requires to watch two excerpt movie scene. In the end, we ask the participant to address what feeling drew from the scene, from themselves and from the character.

Right to withdraw Participants have the right to withdraw from the research at any time for whatever reason. Participants can also request at any time to have their response data removed from record.

Are there any benefits from my participation? While there will be no direct benefit from participation studies like this can make an important contribution to our understanding this topic further. As such, the findings from this study may be presented at national and international conferences and will be submitted for publication in peer-reviewed journals. Interim and final reports will be prepared. However no individual participant will be identified in any publication or presentation. Individuals will not be offered any monetary or other rewards for their participation.

Are there any risks involved in participation? There are no known risks associated with participation. Any inconvenience involved in taking part will be limited. After participation, a debriefing stage will be offered where any further questions will be answered, or any questions can be emailed to my email address below.

Confidentiality All individual information collected as part of the study will be used solely for experimental purposes. They will be stored safely and will not be publicly displayed or published without prior consent. Data collected is stored in the EU, for five years, and will be used for research purposes to generate research content such as publications and presentations.

Please note this research has been ethically approved by the DBS College Human Research Ethics Committee.

Contact Details

Should you require any further information about the research, please contact

Karina Moreira Ferreira, 10566988@mydbs.ie My supervisor can be contacted at niall.bourke@dbs.ie

Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey.

Consent Form

A Study of Film & Emotions

I have read and understood the attached Information Sheet regarding this study.

Yes / No

I have had the opportunity to ask questions and discuss the study with the researcher and I have received satisfactory answers to all my questions.

Yes / No

I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason and without this affecting my training.

Yes / No

I agree to take part in the study, the results of which will be published.

Yes / No

I agree to have my data relating to this study to be stored confidentially as described in the Information Sheet.

Yes / No

I'm above 18 years old and consent to participating in the study.

Yes / No

The screenshot shows a Google Forms interface for a survey titled "Film & Emotion". The form is titled "Film & Emotion" and is categorized under "Information". The form content includes the following text:

Information

My name is Karina Moreira Ferreira and I am conducting research in the Department of Psychology at Dublin Business School (DBS) that explores how fictional characters in movies are capable of enable emotions on the audience. This research is being conducted as part of my studies and will be submitted for examination. You are invited to participate in a research study that will form the basis for an undergraduate thesis. Please read the following information before deciding whether to participate.

What are the objectives of the study? The nature of this study is to understand to what extend characters emotions in a movie can drive our own emotions. A full debrief will be offered after participation, where any questions additional will be answered following participation.

Why have I been asked to participate? I would like to collect information from different people regarding their emotions towards a fictional character.

- Participant must have internet access
- The use of headphones is indicated for better appreciation of the video but is not mandatory.

What does participation involve? requires to watch two excerpt movie scenes. In the end, we ask the participant to address what feeling drew from the scene.

The form interface includes a header with "Forms", "Film & Emotion - Saved", and a user profile icon "KF". Below the header, there are tabs for "Questions" and "Responses (35)", and buttons for "Preview", "Style", and "Collect responses". The background of the form is a blue film strip graphic.

Forms Film & Emotion - Saved

Questions Responses 35 Preview Style Collect responses

Right to withdraw Participants have the right to withdraw from the research at any time for whatever reason. Participants can also request at any time to have their response data removed from record.

Are there any benefits from my participation? While there will be no direct benefit from participation studies like this can make an important contribution to our understanding this topic further. As such, the findings from this study may be presented at national and international conferences and will be submitted for publication in peer-reviewed journals. Interim and final reports will be prepared. However no individual participant will be identified in any publication or presentation. Individuals will not be offered any monetary or other rewards for their participation.

Are there any risks involved in participation? There are no known risks associated with participation. Any inconvenience involved in taking part will be limited. After participation, a debriefing stage will be offered where any further questions will be answered, or any questions can be emailed to my email address below.

Confidentiality All individual information collected as part of the study will be used solely for experimental purposes. They will be stored safely and will not be publicly displayed or published without prior consent. Data collected will be anonymous and stored safely in the EU, for five years, and will be used for research purposes to generate research content such as publications and presentations. Please note this research has been ethically approved by the DBS College Human Research Ethics Committee.

Contact Details
Should you require any further information about the research, please contact
Karina Moreira Ferreira, 10566988@mydbs.ie My supervisor can be contacted at niall.bourke@dbs.ie
Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey.

P.S.: This survey contains credits to get free survey responses at SurveySwap.io

Forms Film & Emotion - Saved

Questions Responses 35 Preview Style Collect responses

Section 1

Consent Form
A Study of Film & Emotions

1

I have read and understood the attached Information Sheet regarding this study. *

Yes

No

Forms Film & Emotion - Saved

Questions Responses 35 Preview Style Collect responses

2

I have had the opportunity to ask questions and discuss the study with the researcher and I have received satisfactory answers to all my questions. *

Yes

No

3

I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study at any time without giving a reason and without this affecting my training. *

Yes

No

Forms Film & Emotion - Saved

Questions Responses 35 Preview Style Collect responses

4

I agree to take part in the study, the results of which will be published. *

Yes

No

5

I agree to have my data relating to this study to be stored confidentially as described in the Information Sheet. *

Yes

No

Forms Film & Emotion - Saved

Questions Responses 35 Preview Style Collect responses

5

I agree to have my data relating to this study to be stored confidentially as described in the Information Sheet. *

Yes

No

6

I'm above 18 years old and consent to participating in the study. *

Yes

No

B) Instructions

You are going to watch 2(two) excerpt movie scenes in a total of 5'33". if possible, choose a quiet place and use headphones to a better experience.

After, you will be directed to complete a questionnaire about the emotions experienced by the scenes.

There is no time limit to finish. The estimated time to complete the experiment is approximately 10-15 minutes.

Relax and enjoy the next few minutes!

The screenshot shows a Google Forms interface for a survey titled "Film & Emotion". The form is in "Preview" mode. The top navigation bar includes "Forms", "Film & Emotion - Saved", a help icon, and a user profile icon labeled "KF". Below the navigation bar, there are tabs for "Questions" and "Responses" (with a count of 35). Action buttons for "Preview", "Style", and "Collect responses" are visible. The main content area displays "Section 2" with a title "Instructions" and a list of four bullet points:

- You are going to watch 2(two) excerpt movie scenes in a total of 5'33". if possible, choose a quiet place and use headphones to a better experience.
- After, you will be directed to complete a questionnaire about the emotions experienced by the scenes.
- There is no time limit to finish. The estimated time to complete the experiment is approximately 10-15 minutes.
- Relax and enjoy the next few minutes!

C) Video Stimuli

<https://youtu.be/H9rEMtBpcwM> (Positive Music)

<https://youtu.be/8ExMrtANLpw> (Negative Music)

<https://youtu.be/6jTJ2vuBpto> (Original scene - no music)

The image shows a screenshot of a Google Forms interface. The top navigation bar is teal and contains the text "Forms", "Film & Emotion - Saved", and a user profile icon labeled "KF". Below the navigation bar, there are tabs for "Questions" and "Responses" (with a count of 35). To the right of these tabs are buttons for "Preview", "Style", and "Collect responses". The main content area features a video player with a blue filmstrip background. The video player shows a man in a plaid shirt smiling, with a red play button in the center. The video player interface includes a "Video 2" title, a "Share" icon, and a "Watch on YouTube" link at the bottom. The video player is set within a white frame against the blue filmstrip background.

D) Debrief Section

Your participation is now finished.

Thank you again for your contribution on this study about film & emotions. The results will broaden and enrich our knowledge of this fascinating area of Psychology.

If you have any question or concern regarding this study, please, do not hesitate to contact the researcher (10566988@mydbs.ie) for more information.

If for any reason you felt distressed during the experiment and this feeling persisted after, we encourage you to contact the following support groups:

AWARE: 1800 80 48 48

The Samaritans: 11612

The screenshot shows a survey platform interface. At the top, there is a green header with 'Forms' on the left, 'Film & Emotion - Saved' in the center, and a user profile icon 'KF' on the right. Below the header, there are tabs for 'Questions' and 'Responses' (with '35' next to it). To the right of these tabs are buttons for 'Preview', 'Style', and 'Collect responses'. The main content area is titled 'Section 5' and contains a 'Debrief Session' section. The text in this section reads: 'Your participation is now finished.' followed by a thank you message, contact information for the researcher, support group information, and a link to SurveySwap.io for credits. The background of the survey page features a blue film strip graphic.

Forms Film & Emotion - Saved ? KF

Questions Responses 35 Preview Style Collect responses

Section 5

Debrief Session

Your participation is now finished.

Thank you again for your contribution on this study about film & emotions. The results will broaden and enrich our knowledge of this fascinating area of Psychology.

If you have any question or concern regarding this study, please, do not hesitate to contact the researcher (10566988@mydbs.ie) for more information.

If for any reason you felt distressed during the experiment and this feeling persisted after, we encourage you to contact the following support groups:

AWARE: 1800 80 48 48
The Samaritans: 11612

The following code gives you credits that can be used to get free research participants at [SurveySwap.io](https://surveyswap.io).

Go to: <https://surveyswap.io/sr/NF0S-8IZR-79EU>

Or, alternatively, enter the code manually: NF0S-8IZR-79EU

E) The Discrete Emotion Questionnaire

Please indicate your response using the scale provided.

While (*undergoing the emotional experience, e.g., viewing the photographs, reading the story, etc.*) to what extent did you experience these emotions?

F)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Not at all	Slightly	Somewhat	Moderately	Quite a bit	Very Much	An extreme amount
Anger							
Wanting							
Dread							
Sad							
Easygoing							
Grossed out							
Happy							
Terror							
Rage							
Grief							
Nausea							
Anxiety							
Chilled out							
Desire							
Nervous							
Lonely							
Nausea							
Anxiety							
Chilled out							
Desire							
Nervous							
Lonely							
Scared							
Mad							
Satisfaction							
Sickened							
Empty							
Craving							
Panic							
Longing							
Calm							
Fear							
Relaxation							
Revulsion							
Worry							
Enjoyment							
Pissed off							
Liking							

Ag = Anger items (anger, rage, mad, pissed off)
Dg = Disgust items (grossed out, nausea, sickened, revulsion)
F = Fear items (terror, scared, panic, fear)
Ax = Anxiety items (dread, anxiety, nervous, worry)
S = Sadness items (sad, grief, lonely, empty)
Dr = Desire items (wanting, desire, craving, longing)
R = Relaxation items (easy going, chilled out, calm, relaxation)
H = Happiness items (happy, satisfaction, enjoyment, liking).

*The final scores include the sum of the items for each discrete emotion category.